

**SOCIAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL DETERMINANTS AND ISSUES OF
PREVENTION OF INTERNET ADDICTION IN YOUTH****Khatamova Dilafruz Aminovna**

teacher,

Navoi State Pedagogical Institute,

Faculty of Medicine, Department of "General Medical Sciences"

Abstract: The article describes social networks and today's young people's views on social networks, how they use the Internet, their positive and negative aspects, and psychological analysis.

Key words: globalization, culture, social network, internet, mass media, ideological attack, virtual communication, ideological fields.

Currently, a large number of people around the world use Internet services and exchange information.

Today, regardless of age, gender, social level, Internet users are increasing.

Since the advent of the Internet, some have praised it, while others have criticized it. The accepted view on this subject is that the Internet is a medium like television and radio. If we use it for good, it is good, if we use it for evil, it becomes something bad. The most important factor here is the human factor.

Effective use of computer technologies and the Internet among the population and young people is desirable. This is based on the fact that the third initiative of the "5 important initiatives to raise the morale of young people and meaningfully organize their free time" adopted by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoev is aimed at "Organizing the effective use of computer technologies and the Internet among the population and young people." not for nothing. It should be noted that the implementation of new modern information and communication technologies (ICT) system and the possibilities of the Internet means that the process of providing

education to the youth of our country in accordance with the requirements of the times is a factor of increasing its effectiveness.

One of the advantages of new modern technologies is that effective use of ICT system and Internet network, which is rapidly developing in the world, allows young people to develop their creative thinking and show their identity. This requires providing our young people with all the necessary technical tools in accordance with the needs of the times, in order to demonstrate their intellectual potential and abilities, in the process of education and training, including the organization of purposeful and meaningful use of the Internet system.

According to the expert's information, the number of users of the Internet system in our country is about 12.1 million, in other words, one third of the population of our republic regularly uses the Internet¹. This, of course, indicates that information and communication technologies are rapidly developing in our country, and that there are opportunities to use high-quality communication systems in the implementation of the constitutional rights of our citizens, such as receiving, storing, and distributing information. Today, the majority of Internet users are young people, and a large part of it is accounted for by students. Therefore, it is emphasized that these new technologies have a negative impact on the education of children and young people if the experts, doctors, pedagogues, scientists do not give advice and instructions to the students who use the Internet, or if they are not completely controlled. Because today's globalization process, the "race" of active use of various information fields to occupy the spiritual world of young people is accelerating. In order to prevent such danger, first of all, it is necessary to form the culture of using the Internet among students in educational institutions.

It is known that the role and importance of the school educational institution in educating the young generation, forming a well-rounded generation, educating young people spiritually, morally and physically healthy, turning them into active participants of the ongoing reforms, using the achievements of technical and advanced

technologies, the Internet and social networks big The goal is to protect young people from the influence of foreign ideas, to educate them in the spirit of loyalty to national and universal values, religious tolerance and inter-ethnic harmony, to implement measures against the penetration of foreign "popular culture" among students and young people, and to form ideological immunity in them. Relevance of the topic. In his address to the Oliy Majlis, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, declared 2020 as the "Year of Development of Science and Digital Economy", along with the recognition of the mutual harmony of the fields of education and science, the implementation of the state's youth policy, new modern methods of education, including it is not an exaggeration if it is considered a practical expression of the fact that special attention is paid to the introduction of information and communication technologies. Today, our society is interested in educating a new generation of enterprising reformers, strategic thinkers, educated and qualified personnel.

As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted, "Where there is no knowledge, there will be backwardness, ignorance and, of course, going astray." As the sages of the East say, "The greatest wealth is intelligence and knowledge, the greatest inheritance is a good education, and the greatest poverty is ignorance!" Therefore, for our youth, acquiring modern knowledge, becoming the owner of true enlightenment and high culture should become a continuous vital need.

Today, information technology is deeply penetrating all areas of the world. As stated in the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis, "To date, more than 7,000 healthcare, preschool educational institutions and schools have been connected to high-speed Internet, and in the next 2 years, another 12,000 institutions will be connected to high-speed Internet."

Necessary technological conditions and legal guarantees have been created for the purpose of spiritual growth of the growing young generation, realization of their rights to information, and ensuring freedom of information.

The constitutional norms regarding everyone's freedom of thought and speech, seeking, receiving and disseminating the information they want are specified in our national laws. Norms recognizing the creation of conditions for free use of international information networks and the Internet have been reflected in our laws. In particular, today, in the field of information, mass media, including television, Internet cafes, Internet providers, state information resources, "ZiyoNet", "Lex.uz", "Kitob.uz" youth information portals and information-library institutions are operating. It is necessary to make good use of it in such a period created by our state.

Currently, more than 1,400 mass media are operating in our country¹. Today, in addition to traditional mass media such as newspapers, magazines, radio and television, digital and mobile television, internet newspapers and internet radio are taking a strong place in the national information space of our country.

Currently, their number has exceeded 330. Also, more than 60 TV channels serve to satisfy various informational needs and interests of the youth audience. These media contribute to the formation of information culture and ideological immunity of the younger generation. In particular, providing educational institutions with computer equipment, using modern methods of teaching, using information resource centers in all educational institutions gives an opportunity to further increase educational opportunities. Of these, the Ziya Net public information and education network is currently doing significant work in providing information and communication services to young people and students. However, there is another side of the issue: in what way are young people using the created opportunities? How do these opportunities affect their development? - painful questions arise.

Nowadays, 90 percent of young people turn to the Internet as their main source of information. Most of the used media are social networks and video and audio portals

such as "Twitter", "Facebook", "Odnoklassniki", "YouTube". According to data, today there are more than 9 thousand sites promoting easy ways to commit suicide on the Internet, while 49 percent of computer games promote violence and evil. At the same time, 42 percent of children and adolescents have been completely exposed to pornography distributed online.

International experts confirm that 38% of children regularly visit websites with a spirit of violence, and 26% visit nationalistic web pages. In the process of information globalization, formation of the national information space, protection and creation of organizational and legal frameworks for its development are among the priority tasks that are aligned with the strategic interests of each country. The further increase in the pace of development of information and communication technologies creates unlimited opportunities in the field of information exchange. This, in turn, has become one of the main factors of the socio-political and economic development of the countries of the world.

In the 20th century, nuclear weapons posed a threat to humanity, but by the 21st century, information attacks organized under the guise of religion for various purposes are endangering the whole world. The Internet has become one of the mass media with a strong social impact.

In recent years, various social networks have become an integral part of the Internet world. So what is a social network itself? Let's clarify this issue. Internet networks (sites) that provide "online" acquaintance and communication between people remotely via the Internet and reflect various personal information of their members are called social networks. In the whirlpool of social networks such as "Facebook", "Odnoklassniki.ru", "Telegram", "Mail.ru", various vices are forming among students. Now, the struggles in the ideological arenas, not the nuclear arenas, will decide many things. Therefore, at a time when the ideological, ideological and informational threat is increasing in the modern international information space, it is necessary to organize spiritual and educational activities based on the needs of the

times, to protect young people from ideological attacks, and to form a conscious attitude to life in them.

Educational processes are also directly related to the Internet today. So today, students should be protected from such spiritual threats.

According to the research conducted by psychologists, 15-25 percent of the population is addicted to critical assimilation of information, and the remaining 75 percent are influenced by the received information². The role of social media in our daily lives cannot be denied. But we cannot turn a blind eye to the dangerous aspects that students sacrifice not only their time but also their mental health on social networks. It seeks to compensate for the shortcomings, frustrations and failures of the life of students in the network. Pictures and comments on them, new friends, bright pictures and cross-network associations excite a person.

The Internet will completely change their thinking. In addition, social networks can serve the evil purposes of malicious people. The object of the subject. Increasing the culture of using the Internet and social networks among students and young people in school educational institutions. Analyze their pros and cons. Study of the topic. The socio-political changes taking place in the world today have different effects on the minds of students. Several researchers have studied the role of electronic media and Internet networks in the process of globalization, their influence on moral and aesthetic education processes, what consequences they cause, and measures to eliminate them.

Today is the age of information. The modern information field is fast, its scope is also wide and impressive. For this reason, in the process of social-spiritual, political-legal education in our country, it is necessary to expand the possibilities of mass media.

In the era of globalization, there is an unprecedented battle for the hearts and minds of the youth. The impact of such a threat can be observed first of all in some sources and news media that have become an ideological threat. Young people who do not have life experience can accept this information as real truth and be deceived by lies and fabrications. To prevent such situations, it is necessary to implement the

following; - formation of the culture of using the Internet and social networks; - formation of national mentality in the minds of students; - creation of universal ideological immunity; - educate them in the spirit of national values; - meaningful spending of educational hours in spiritual and moral education of students; - Parents should pay attention to their children's upbringing.

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